

Table S2. Ethnolinguistic characteristics of studied Uralic-speaking populations

Population	Country	No. of speakers [*]	Language subgroup ^{**}
Saami	Finland/Sweden/Norway/Russia	23 300 ¹	Saami
Finn ^{***}	Finland	4 869 362 ²	Finnic
Estonian	Estonia	886 859 ³	Finnic
Karelian	Russia	60 815 ⁵	Finnic
Vepsian	Russia	5 936 ⁵	Finnic
Mari	Russia	547 605 ⁵	Mari
Mordovian	Russia	744 237 ⁵	Mordvin
Udmurt	Russia	552 299 ⁵	Permian
Komi	Russia	322 691 ⁵	Permian
Khanty	Russia	30 943 ⁵	Ob-Ugric
Mansi	Russia	12 269 ⁵	Ob-Ugric
Hungarian	Hungary	9 896 333 ⁶	Ugric
Nenets	Russia	44 640 ⁵	Samoyed
Nganasan	Russia	862 ⁵	Samoyed
Selkup	Russia	3 649 ⁵	Samoyed

^{*} no. of speakers of given language can be much smaller than the no. of individuals with self-reported ethnicity in a population and is given only for shown country

^{**} according to Korhonen, M. (1981). *Johdatus lapin kielen historiaan* (Helsinki: Suomalaisen Kirjallisuuden Seura)

^{***} includes also Ingrian Finns

¹ Lewis, M.P., Simons, G.F., and Fennig, C.D. (2016). *Ethnologue: Languages of the World* (Dallas: SIL International).

² Finnish census 2011 http://www.stat.fi/til/vaerak/index_en.html

³ Estonian census 2011 <http://www.stat.ee/phc2011>

⁴ according to the All-Russian population census 2002, from <http://www.suri.ee/uralic.html>

⁵ according to the All-Russian population census 2010 http://www.gks.ru/free_doc/new_site/perepis2010/croc/Documents/Vol4/pub-04-01.pdf

⁶ according to Hungarian census 2011 http://www.ksh.hu/nepszamlalas/tables_regional_00?lang=en